

ARTISANAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR AND PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF GOVERNMENT SUPPORT AND ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to examine the impact of artisanal women entrepreneur on the performance through mediating role of government support and entrepreneurial competencies. The research is of quantitative based, and data is collected using purposive sampling technique through Likert scale, closed ended questionnaires from sample of 402 artisanal women entrepreneurs of Pakistan. To analyze the relationship between variables, structural equation and bootstrap estimates are used on smart PLS. The empirical evidence shows that the artisanal women's entrepreneurial competencies have positive impact on entrepreneurs' performance but artisanal women who rely on government support don't perform well. Firstly, country specific sample is used which limit the generalizability. Secondly, the busy schedule, literacy rate, cultural, religious, and privacy concern restrain women to disclose information. Thirdly, only two moderators are incorporated in the study. The novelty of this research resides in the evidence to support mediating role of entrepreneurial skills of women and performance in resource-scarce contexts. This study demonstrates that female entrepreneurs who uses their entrepreneurial skills, perform better than those who rely solely on government assistance. Policy makers will establish policies for artisanal women entrepreneurs to promote gender equality at the societal and organizational levels.

KEYWORDS: Artisanal women entrepreneur, Entrepreneurial orientation, Entrepreneurial Competencies

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between entrepreneurship, business growth and its contribution to economic development is a key factor for the research on this phenomenon. Since 1988, number of women come with the decision to start their own enterprises and has increased intensely over the time (Helms & M. M, 1997). Women are taking part to improve their lives and to contribute to the economy (Kermel-Torres et al, 1994). In developing nations, artisanal activities play a significant role in generating economic options and improving the financial situation of women and their families. An artisan is a person who uses their hands to produce distinctive, useful, and/or decorative objects using conventional methods but what separates female entrepreneurs who succeed their businesses (Dawa, Namatovu, Mulira, & Kyejjusa, 2021).

Hisrich et al. (1999) assert that a variety of factors, including entrepreneurial skills and government backing, can have an impact on performance. According to researchers, government support highly effects the performances of business (Boohene et al, 2012; Hinton et al, 2003) and some researchers states that entrepreneurial competencies and firm growth are directly linked (Nassium et al, 2014; Sathya & Vithyapriya, 2016). As entrepreneurial competencies increase the performance directly and government support effect performance by devising appropriate policies and providing infrastructure, an entrepreneur can gain benefits by adopting entrepreneurial competencies and support of the government (Basu & A, 1998; Man et al, 2008). It has been established that an entrepreneur's success is influenced by a friendly culture and government legislation (Shakeel, Yaokuang, & Gohar, 2020). But women entrepreneurs of Pakistan suffer in several areas, including access to capital, family size, and the political and cultural climate. Women in societies where men predominate are discriminated against because society believes that women are incapable of being business owners (Godwin et al., 2006; Ufuk and Zgen, 2001).

In Pakistan, women make about half of the population, and the Labor Force Survey estimates that 13.3 million of them are employed. Women equally help to the males to earn bread and increase the lifestyle of their life (Merlo et al, 2019). Women are also dominate in artisanal activities (Igwe et al, 2019). If they are given more opportunities and assistance from the government, their contributions can increase even further. Unfortunately, there is a void that effectively halts the idea of artisanal female entrepreneurship. Researchers should focus on the characteristics of women that directly affect their capabilities and empowerment and lead them to become more involved in entrepreneurial processes (De Bruin et al, 2006).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. ARTISANAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR AND PERFORMANCE

Women entrepreneurship is not new field, and it is also growing worldwide (Sathya & Vithyapriya, 2016). Women entrepreneurs can compete in the market and women's entrepreneurship, and empowering women in business is an

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important for a nation's growth (Ismail et al, 2018). Females and males both participate in performances equally, and women can compete with men in every area of the work (Abu Bakar et al, 2016). In terms of economic growth, job creation, and active participation in the economy, women's contributions have increased (Merlo et al, 2019; Osondu & C. K, 2015). According to the researchers, entrepreneurial competencies and government support helps entrepreneurial women to be successful in the business (Agarwal et al, 2018; Kiggundu and M. N, 2002). Based on the above-reviewed literature, this study will only focus on the direct effects of artisanal production on economic performance and on the following hypothesis emerges from the literature.

H1: There is a relationship between artisanal women entrepreneur and performance

2.2. ARTISANAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR AND ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES

Performance and growth are affected by entrepreneurial competencies (Mitchelmore et al, 2013) which are considered substantial resources of SME business (Tehseen et al, 2015). When an entrepreneur can locate and use the resources required to achieve the goals of the firm, they are competent (Mitchelmore and Rowley, 2013). The most of women-owned enterprises heavily reliant on their owner abilities (Kyejjusa et al., 2016; Lerner et al., 1997). Performance will be affected if an artisanal woman entrepreneur is persistent, dedicated to their work, willing to take risks, effective, goal-oriented, information-seeking, systematic in their planning, persuasive in their networking, and self-assured (Kyndt et al, 2015).

H2: There is a relationship between artisanal women entrepreneur and entrepreneurial Competences

2.3. ARTISANAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR AND GOVERNMENT SUPPORT

Government support has a big impact on how artisanal women entrepreneurs perform. If the government supports an artisanal woman entrepreneur, it will inspire them and improve their performance compared to before. The government assistance can take the form of financial aid or even cost-free training. The government can also help in controlling factors such as local economic development, trade openness, financial development, and industrial structure ((Boohene et al., 2012; Guang-Jian et al, 2016). With increasing role of women entrepreneur in development of their own lives and economy growth, government agencies can play vital role for the success of their initiates ((Basu & A, 1998; Shah and H, 2013; Kermel-Torres et al, 1994). This study will solely focus on the direct effect of government support on performance. It is also assumed that the essential component of performance is the artisanal woman entrepreneur.

H3: There is a relationship between artisanal women entrepreneur and government support

2.4. ARTISANAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR, GOVERNMENT SUPPORT AND PERFORMANCE

Personal characteristics of an entrepreneur, such as risk-taking, confidence, motivation, and goals orientation have an impact on how well their business performs. An entrepreneur must possess personal effective on performance (Cooper & Gascon, 1992). Successful entrepreneurship is based on entrepreneurial competencies (Al Mamun et al, 2016; Sinyolo et al, 2018) and Performance is also improved with more education in entrepreneurship (Box et al, 1993). Artisanal Women Entrepreneur performance can be enhanced by the support of government (Mensah and Benedict et al, 2010). This study will examine how government assistance to artisanal women entrepreneurs will impact their performance.

H4: Government support will mediate the relationship between artisanal women entrepreneur and performance

2.5. ARTISANAL WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR, ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES AND PERFORMANCE

Women are taking equal part to earn livelihood (Hilson et al, 2018) and there is a need to promote artisanal activities because artisanal women entrepreneurs make up a large portion of small businesses. Artisanal Women-owned SME businesses contribute significantly contribute to the advancement of society and progress of country (DRIS et al., 2016; Guzmán & J. N. C, 2020). Entrepreneurial competencies or psychological motivation have prominent difference on growth, and these competencies are essential for success (Brockhaus & Horwitz, 1986). Entrepreneurs who adopt entrepreneurial competencies succeed in expanding their businesses and advancing the economy (Brockhaus & Horwitz, 1987; Miskin & Rose, 1999). As a result, this study tries to explain how entrepreneurial skills will impact that how well artisanal women entrepreneurs perform.

H5: Entrepreneurial competencies will mediate the relationship between artisanal women entrepreneur and performance

2.6. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Discussion in a literature review explains the conceptual relationship between the variables. The artisanal women entrepreneurs. Performance is effectiveness of them is directly impacted by these variables. Artisanal Women-owned small and medium businesses play a essential role in business growth on a national and international level (Guzmán & J. N. C, 2020). According to Sánchez and J. C. (2013) entrepreneurial education programs that focus on entrepreneurial competencies will enhances the chances of new startups and female artisanal entrepreneurs have a direct impact on performance. Performance will change if the government supports artisanal women entrepreneurs. As Doh et al. (2014) stated that government support policies have an impact on innovative in SME's. Government assistance and entrepreneurial skills have an indirect impact on artisanal women business owners. Innovations theory support the relationship between performance and artisanal women entrepreneurs. Effectuation theory states that the success of women is influenced by their leadership potential, self-awareness, social awareness, ability to spot opportunities, risk-taking, and other marketable skills. Entrepreneurial women excel at social entrepreneurship (Agarwal et al, 2020)

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. Data Collection and Analysis

The study uses primary data which was collected using questionnaires. The convenience sampling technique was used to collect the data from Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs of Pakistan. The researchers used various rigorous methodologies (Cronbach’s alpha, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, and Regression Analysis) internal consistency of the data goodness of variables. The econometric model to was estimated using SPSS 23 and Smart PLS3.

3.1. RELIABILITY: CRONBACH’S ALPHA

Using Cronbach's alpha, scales' collective reliability and internal consistency were examined. The Cronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.70 (see Table 1), indicating that the scales are internally consistent.

Table 1: Collective Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
.744	13

The Questionnaire items are scored using a Likert scale with a maximum of five points, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Table 2 shows the items' individual consistency and reliability. AWE, P, and GS each have two items, whereas EC has five. All items have a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.70, which indicates high reliability.

Table 2: Individual Items Reliability

Sr. No	Variable	No of items	Cronbach alpha	Range
1	AWE	2	.712	>0.7
2	P	2	.766	>0.7
3	GS	2	.883	>0.7
4	EC	7	.917	>0.7

Note: P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

3.2. CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS (CFA)

Confirmatory factor analysis is used to evaluate the model's validity. The results of the CFA analysis about the model's good fit are satisfactory; see figure 2. We can see the results of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in the diagram. All statements have outer loading values of 0.70 or higher, which is great and acceptable (see Table 3).

The values of discriminant validity with respect to various variables are also shown in the figure. AWE's validity value when compared to EC is 0.730. AWE's validity value when compared to GS is -0.387. The value of GS with P is 0.076 and the EC with P has a value of 0.363. AWE's validity score with P is 0.140. In the below diagram, it can be seen how one variable is related to another. As we can see, the AWE arrow is turning toward GS, and its value is 1.50. The AWE arrow, which points toward the EC and value is 0.533. Three arrows are heading in P's direction, and P has a value of 0.204.

Figure 1: CFA

Table 3: Outer Loadings

Items	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE1	0.738			
AWE2	0.749			
EC1		0.717		
EC2		0.859		
EC3		0.766		
EC4		0.926		
EC5		0.753		
EC6		0.738		
EC7		0.711		
GS1			0.863	
GS2			0.916	
P1				0.699
P2				0.890

AWE1: Artisanal women entrepreneur’s statement 1, AWE2: Artisanal women entrepreneur’s statement 2, P1: Performance’s statement 1, P2: Performance’s statement 2, GS1: Government support’s statement 1, GS2: Government support’s statement 2, EC1: Entrepreneurial Competencies’ statement 1, EC2: Entrepreneurial Competencies’ statement 2, EC3: Entrepreneurial Competencies’ statement 3, EC4: Entrepreneurial Competencies’ statement 4, EC5: Entrepreneurial Competencies’ statement 5, EC6: Entrepreneurial Competencies’ statement 6 and EC7: Entrepreneurial Competencies’ statement 7.

3.3. TOTAL INDIRECT EFFECTS

The table below shows how government assistance and entrepreneurial skills have an impact on the performance of artisanal women entrepreneurs. The *P* value of 0.233 shows insignificant effect.

Table 4: Total Indirect Effects

	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE				0.233
EC				
GS				
P				

3.4. SPECIFIC INDIRECT EFFECT

It can be observed from the table 5 that government support has negative and insignificant impact on the performance of artisanal women entrepreneurs. And Entrepreneurial skills has positive but insignificant impact on performance of artisanal women entrepreneurs.

Table 5: Specific Indirect Effect

Specific Indirect Effects	
AWE -> GS -> P	-0.030
AWE -> EC -> P	0.265

3.5. TOTAL EFFECTS

Empirical evidence indicate that government support and entrepreneurial skills have an impact on the performance of artisanal women entrepreneurs. The artisanal women entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial skills has a value of 0.730, showing significant result. Government assistance and artisanal women entrepreneurs have a net impact of -0.387. The results are not statistically significant. The relationship between performance and artisanal women entrepreneurs is 0.377 and these results are not statistically significant. Entrepreneurial skills and performance have a 0.363 value which means results are not statistically significant. Government assistance and performance have a value of 0.076. The results are not statistically significant.

Table 6: Total Effects

AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE	0.730	-0.387	0.377
EC			0.363
GS			0.076
P			

3.6. RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

Table 7: Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
AWE	0.712	0.712	0.712	0.553
EC	0.918	0.923	0.918	0.616
GS	0.883	0.885	0.884	0.792
P	0.767	0.799	0.779	0.641

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

3.7. CRONBACH'S ALPHA

Cronbach's Alpha, which ranges from 0.7 to 0.9, should be higher than the acceptable value of 0.7. The acceptable Cronbach's Alpha AWE value is 0.712, which is larger than 0.7. The EC value is 0.918, which is outstanding and higher than 0.7. The GS value is 0.918, which is outstanding and higher than 0.7. P value is 0.767, higher than 0.7 and in the range of 0.7 to 0.9. The results of Cronbach's Alpha are all positive and satisfactory. Graphic analysis makes easier to understand the result. The Cronbach's Alpha graph clearly shows positive results. Each variable's bar is higher than 0.7 and has a value between 0.7 and 0.9 (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Cronbach's Alpha

3.8. RHO A

rbo A, which ranges from 0.7 to 0.9, should be higher than the acceptable value of 0.7. The rbo A graph (see Figure 4) shows positive results. Each variable's bar is higher than 0.7 and has a value between 0.7 and 0.9

Figure 4: rho A

3.9. COMPOSITE RELIABILITY

The values of Composite reliability values are all good and acceptable because values are greater than 0.70 as shown in the Figure 5.

Figure 5: Composite Reliability

3.10. AVERAGE VARIANCE EXTRACTED

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) number need to be higher than 0.5. The Average variance extracted (AWE) value is 0.553, which is larger than 0.5. The good EC value of 0.616 is greater than 0.5. The GS value is 0.792, which is outstanding and higher than 0.5. P value is 0.641, which is acceptable as it is higher than 0.5. The average variation extracted values are all good and acceptable. (See Figure 6)

Figure 6: Average Variance Extracted

3.11. DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY: FORNELL-LARCKER CRITERION

Diagonal values ought to be higher than lower diagonal values, according to the Fornell-Larcker criteria. It is crucial to fulfil this requirement. The diagonal values in the preceding table are 0.744 for AWE, 0.785 for EC, 0.890 for GS, and 0.800 for P. The lower numbers in the AWE column are 0.730, -0.387, and 0.373, as can be seen. These numbers are under 0.744. Lower values in EC are 0.440 and -0.330. These numbers are lower than 0.785. The GS column's bottom value is -0.097. This number is below 0.890. Fornell-conditions Larcker's are thus satisfied.

Table 8: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE	0.744			
EC	0.730	0.785		
GS	-0.387	-0.330	0.890	
P	0.375	0.440	-0.097	0.800

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

3.12. CROSS LOADING

In cross loading, Variables should represent its own variable more in his column. In AWE1, AWE value is 0.738 which is higher than t the EC value 0.539, GS value -0.257 and P value 0.309. In AWE2, AWE value is 0.749 which is higher than t the EC value 0.546, GS value -0.318 and P value 0.249. In EC1, EC value is 0.717 which is higher than t the AWE value 0.531, GS value -0.282 and P value 0.249. In EC2, EC value is 0.859 which is higher than the AWE value 0.586, GS value -0.246 and P value 0.437. In EC3, EC value is 0.766 which is higher than the AWE value 0.598, GS value -0.256 and P value 0.278. In EC4, EC value is 0.926 which is higher than the AWE value 0.665, GS value -0.277 and P value 0.423. In EC5, EC value is 0.753 which is higher than the AWE value 0.551, GS value -0.295 and P value 0.330. In EC6, EC value is 0.738 which is higher than the AWE value 0.538, GS value -0.194 and P value 0.325. In EC7, EC value is 0.711 which is higher than the AWE value 0.531, GS value -0.266 and P value 0.294. In GS1, GS value is 0.863 which is higher than the AWE value -0.331, EC value -0.283 and P value -0.095. In GS2, GS value is 0.916 which is higher than the AWE value -0.358, EC value -0.304 and P value -0.078. In P1, P value is 0.699 which is higher than the AWE value 0.267, EC value 0.312 and GS value -0.035. In P2, P value is 0.890 which is higher than the AWE value 0.330, EC value 0.388 and GS value -0.113. So, overall cross loading results are good and acceptable.

Table 9: Cross Loading

	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE1	0.738	0.539	-0.257	0.309
AWE2	0.749	0.546	-0.318	0.249
EC1	0.531	0.717	-0.282	0.304
EC2	0.586	0.859	-0.246	0.437
EC3	0.598	0.766	-0.256	0.278
EC4	0.665	0.926	-0.277	0.423
EC5	0.551	0.753	-0.295	0.330
EC6	0.538	0.738	-0.194	0.325
EC7	0.531	0.711	-0.266	0.294
GS1	-0.331	-0.283	0.863	-0.095
GS2	-0.358	-0.304	0.916	-0.078
P1	0.267	0.312	-0.035	0.699
P2	0.330	0.388	-0.113	0.890

AWE1: Artisanal women entrepreneur's statement 1, AWE2: Artisanal women entrepreneur's statement 2, P1: Performance's statement 1, P2: Performance's statement 2, GS1: Government support's statement 1, GS2: Government support's statement 2, EC1: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 1, EC2: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 2, EC3: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 3, EC4: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 4, EC5: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 5, EC6: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 6 and EC7: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 7.

3.13. HETEROTRAIT-MONOTRAIT RATIO (HTMT)

All values for the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) should be lower than 0.8. All of these are less than 0.80 and acceptable as displayed in Figure 7 and Table 10

Table 10: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE				
EC	0.729			
GS	0.387	0.331		
P	0.379	0.439	0.094	

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

Figure 7: HTMT

3.14. COLLINEARITY STATISTICS (VIF)

Values in the outer VIF should be fewer than 3, any value over 5 is concerning and should be avoided. The VIF table demonstrates that all values fall within the range, proving that the data is homoscedastic.

Table 11: Outer VIF

	VIF
AWE1	1.440
AWE2	1.440
EC1	2.722
EC2	2.888
EC3	2.631
EC4	2.784
EC5	2.144
EC6	2.042
EC7	1.938
GS1	2.664
GS2	2.664
P1	1.633
P2	1.633

AWE1: Artisanal women entrepreneur's statement 1, AWE2: Artisanal women entrepreneur's statement 2, P1: Performance's statement 1, P2: Performance's statement 2, GS1: Government support's statement 1, GS2: Government support's statement 2, EC1: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 1, EC2: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 2, EC3: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 3, EC4: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 4, EC5: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 5, EC6: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 6 and EC7: Entrepreneurial Competencies' statement 7.

All values in the table (Inner VIF Values) below are less than 3, which shows that There is no multicollinearity because the values are acceptable.

Table 12: Inner VIF Values

	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE	1.000		1.000	2.257
EC		1.000		2.152
GS			1.000	1.183
P				1.000

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

3.15. MODEL FIT

The SRMR values in the model fit table are 0.041 for the saturated model and 0.043 for the estimated model, both of which are less than 0.08. It is appropriate. In the saturated model and the approximated model, the NIF values are 0.905 and 0.865, respectively. It is appropriate. Model is thus fitted.

Table 13: Model Fit

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.041	0.043
d_ ULS	0.153	0.169
d_ G	0.131	0.132
Chi-Square	276.0	277.8
NFI	0.906	0.905

3.16. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Table 14: Descriptive Statistics

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
AWE -> EC	0.730	0.731	0.052	13.958	0.000
AWE -> GS	-0.387	-0.387	0.054	7.108	0.000
AWE -> P	0.141	0.139	0.173	0.813	0.416
EC -> P	0.364	0.365	0.141	2.584	0.010
GS -> P	0.078	0.075	0.079	0.981	0.327

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

3.17. REGRESSION ANALYSIS

By choosing a path, the first consistent PLS algorithm was determined. Coefficient, latent variables, *R*-square, adjusted *R*-square, and *F* square are the results shown by the path. The association between artisanal women entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial competencies is strong, according to the results of the consistent PLS algorithm but the relationship of Government support for artisanal entrepreneur is insignificant.

Second, choosing a path led to the discovery of bootstrapping. The *P* value and *t*-statistic were focused on and analyzed to determine the results' significance by using sample of 5000 observations. The findings of bootstrapping show significant association between entrepreneurial competencies and artisanal women entrepreneurs. Government support for artisanal women business owners is not significant. Because there is little association between artisanal women entrepreneurs and government funding.

3.18. PATH COEFFICIENT

Table 15: Path Coefficient

	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE		0.730	-0.387	0.141
EC				0.364
GS				0.078
P				

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

Figure 8: Path Coefficient

In graph, we can analyze easily. The effect of artisanal women entrepreneurs on entrepreneurial competencies is very high. The effect of artisanal women entrepreneurs on entrepreneurial competencies is 0.730 and it is very high. The

effect of artisanal women entrepreneurs on government support is -0.387 and it is negative. The effect of artisanal women entrepreneurs on performance is 0.141 and it is normal. The effect of the entrepreneurial competencies on performance is 0.364 and it is high. Effect of government support on performance is 0.078 and it is not high. The effect of artisanal women entrepreneurs on government support is negative. The effect of artisanal women entrepreneurs on the performance is normal. Effect of entrepreneurial competencies on the performance is high. Effect of government support on performance is not high.

3.19. LATENT VARIABLES

Table 16: Latent Variables

Correlation Analysis				
Variables	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE	1			
EC	0.730	1		
GS	-0.387	-0.330	1	
P	0.377	0.442	-0.097	1

Note: In the values ** is indicate the significances. P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

In above table, AWE and EC have a correlation coefficient of 0.720. AWE's correlation with GS is -0.387. AWE has a P-value correlation of 0.377. The value of the EC correlation with GS is -0.330. The value of the EC correlation with P is 0.442. The value of the GS correlation with P is -0.097.

3.20. R SQUARE

Table 17: R Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
EC	0.533	0.532
GS	0.150	0.148
P	0.207	0.201

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

The findings show that 53% of artisanal women entrepreneurs are influencing entrepreneurial competencies. Artisanal women entrepreneurs are affecting to government support 15%. And 20.7% change in the performance is influenced by Artisanal women entrepreneurs. (See Table 16 & Figure 9)

Figure 9: R Square

Figure 10: R Square Adjusted

3.21. F SQUARE

Table 18: F Square

	AWE	EC	GS	P
AWE		1.140	0.176	0.011
EC				0.078
GS				0.006
P				

P=Performance, EC= Entrepreneurial Competencies, GS= Government Support, AWE= Artisanal Women Entrepreneurs.

The F-value for artisanal women entrepreneurs is 1.140, which is greater than 0.15 and indicates that they have a significant impact on entrepreneurial competencies. AWE are also affecting the government support with F-Value of 0.176 which is more than 0.15 showing substantial impact. Similarly, AWE is affecting the performance and F-Value is 0.011 which is less than 0.15 indicating insignificant impact. Entrepreneurial competencies are affecting to performance and F-value is 0.078 which is less than 0.15 which mean it has insignificant impact. Government support effecting to performance 0.006 which is less than 0.15. (See table 17 &

Figure 11: F Square

4. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examines the determinants that affect artisanal women entrepreneurs' subjective performance. The empirical finding suggests that female entrepreneurs have no discernible impact on subjective performance. Women entrepreneurs perform likewise irrespective of government support. It may be because Government support for artisanal women entrepreneurs in Pakistan is lacking. Entrepreneurial skills act as a mediator and have a significant impact on performance. Women who run successful artisanal businesses are self-motivated and focus on developing their entrepreneurial skills. Government assistance does not have a substantial impact on the performance of artisanal women entrepreneurs. The Pakistani government is lacking to help artisanal women business owners. Additionally, empirical findings show that artisanal women entrepreneurs who possess entrepreneurial skills perform well and that their success is negatively impacted by a lack of government support.

Additionally, it appears that because artisanal women entrepreneurs are self-motivated and do not wait for opportunities, they do not require government backing to succeed in their businesses. Because they allow them to support themselves and serve as a driving force toward financial independence, entrepreneurial skills have a substantial impact on the subjective performance of artisanal women business owners. In light of this, it can be said that artisanal women entrepreneurs who possess entrepreneurial skills perform better than those who rely solely on government assistance.

It is recommended that a framework should be established by government to give training skills to the artisanal women entrepreneurs in Pakistan because they are an asset of our country's culture and should be promoted. Government should support them financially to develop their artisanal products and to promote art and culture of our country. Consequently, by providing necessary entrepreneurial education to artisanal women entrepreneurs in privileged and rural areas will give them a realistic and rational approach to give their concerning outcome and participate more effectively in the development of the economy. Laws should be followed to tackle the negative consequences of women's safety and empowerment. Results showed that the percentage of female participants in rural areas are not touched with technology. So it is necessary that a proper platform should be provided to artisanal women entrepreneurs on which they can establish their business effectively and encourage them by providing easy means and resources.

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